

Effect of Lecturer Certification Allowance, Lecturer Education, and Lecturer Training on Lecturer Performance

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Abstract. This study examines the effect of the certification allowances lecturer, faculty of education, training and lecturer on the performance of the lecturer. This research was conducted using questionnaires to all samples certified lecturer. The data obtained were then processed using regression analysis. The number of questionnaires are processed totaled 75 questionnaire. Hypothesis test results have shown that the benefits of certification lecturers, professors of education, and training faculty positive and significant effect on the performance of the lecturer. Allowances for lecturers who have followed the certification, provide opportunities for continuing education for faculty, and provide training opportunities according to their field can improve the performance of lecturers. The samples in the study have not been evenly distributed and performance assessment are used in the form of self-appraisal, so that further research can be used to sample a wider and performance assessment is done by looking at Work Target Employees for lecturers Civil Servant and the achievement of academic rank private colleges.

Keywords: certification, education, training, lecture performance

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Introduction

The rapid progress in the world of education and the increasingly intense competition that occurs in the future, so it needs a quality generation that can compete with other countries in the world. One way that can be taken to print a quality generation is to provide high quality education. Improving the quality of higher education in Indonesia including the elements that play a role in progress in universities is needed as an effort to improve the quality and quality of higher education.

One of these elements is the educator, the lecturer. Lecturers are required to show good performance. The performance of good lecturers can help universities in achieving the vision and mission of universities. The existence of lecturers at a college is important so it is necessary to evaluate the performance of lecturers.

Higher education as an educational unit that conducts higher education can do several ways to improve lecturer performance, for example through giving allowance to lecturer, giving opportunity to continue education to higher level, and giving opportunity to follow training for lecturer to improve lecturer competence. Through these efforts, it is expected that lecturers will maximize the responsibility for their work because the lecturers have been equipped with education and training related to their implementation of the work, and the provision of allowance to motivate lecturers so that it is expected to affect the lecturer's performance in a better direction (Pramudyo, 2010).

The government has now developed a system of allowances granted to lecturers better known as lecturer certification allowances. The certification allowance is given to lecturers who have followed the lecturer's competency test or lecturer certification. Licensee certification allowance or professional allowance is given as an effort to improve lecturer's performance in university tridharma activity and given the basic salary of the lecturer concerned (Undang-Undang No. 14 Tahun 2005).

Previous research has shown that giving benefits has a positive relationship to one's performance. Other studies also show the result that giving benefits has a significant positive effect on one's performance (Sopiah, 2013; Rizal *et al.*, 2014).

Competence or ability is the capacity of an individual to perform various tasks in a job. A person's ability can be seen from the level of education that has been passed. One's education will

affect one's way of thinking and acting to do a thing, by taking a certain level of education causing a person to have certain knowledge to be capable and capable to perform their duties properly. Thus education will affect a person's performance (Turere, 2013).

The cause of the decline in the performance of a person in an organization is due to a mismatch between the level of ability possessed by a person with the development needs and the dynamics of problems faced by an increasingly competitive world of work. Factors that affect a person's ability are the lack of organizational attention in providing an appropriate training program for his employees.

It can be done by attending lecturers training both inside and outside the city. Lecturers will study knowledge and skills that are practical for a particular purpose and to develop the talents, skills, and abilities of the lecturer in accomplishing specific tasks. Increased scientific knowledge of the lecturer is expected to increase lecturer performance (Turere, 2013).

This research is a development of research on "the influence of training on employee development and performance at Lahore Hotel Industry, Pakistan". The results show that there is a significant influence between training on employee development and performance. Previous research has conducted research on variables that have an influence on one's performance (Sopiah, 2013; Turere, 2013; Ameer & Hanif, 2013).

This research tries to combine these separate variables into one in the study. The object of previous research is employees of a company, so the author is interested to take a different object that is lecturer. The author wants to know whether to give the same or different results with previous research.

Data collection in this research is done by distributing questionnaires to certification lecturers of several universities in Batam. After the questionnaire was distributed, validity and reliability test was conducted to find out whether the questionnaire can be used as a tool to collect data and the data can be analyzed further or not. Empirically the results show that the whole item of statement is valid and reliable. Furthermore, data processing is done by simple linear regression method.

Literature Review

Maslow's Theory

This theory says that basically all humans have basic needs. It shows it in 5 levels of pyramid shape, people start a push from the lowest level. Five levels of need is known as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, starting from the physical needs to the needs of self-actualization. A new higher requirement will arise when the needs below have been fulfilled (Luthans, 2006).

Theory of Self-Effectiveness

An individual's belief that he is capable of completing a given task. Four ways to improve self-effectiveness, that of constant mastery, examples by other individuals, verbal persuasion, and appearance (Robbins, 2005).

Certification Allowance

Certification is the process of certifying educators for teachers and lecturers. Certification program conducted by the government is a breakthrough that is done to improve the quality and competence of teachers or lecturers, so that will have an impact on improving the quality and quality of education. Teachers or lecturers who have attended the certification program and are graduated, the teacher or lecturer will get the educator's certificate, and they will get a benefit known as the certification allowance (Undang-Undang No. 14 Tahun 2005).

The certification allowance is the allowance given to teachers and lecturers who have attended certification. The purpose of certification is to improve the quality of lecturers who ultimately are expected to have an impact on improving the quality of education. Upon passing the certification, the lecturer will also receive a professional allowance (Undang-Undang No. 14 Tahun 2005). By obtaining professional allowance, it is expected to influence the improvement of lecturer's performance.

Education

Education or competence refers to the character of knowledge, skills, and abilities of each individual or personal character that directly affects individual job performance (Yani, 2012). In college, the education of a lecturer is seen as important, because the level of

education owned can reflect the ability and skills in implementing the college tridharma. Lecturers who have a high level of adequate education, is expected to be able to improve its performance as a lecturer.

Training

Training is the process of teaching to new lecturers or lecturers that have been there about the basic skills needed to perform the tasks of the university tridharma especially related to the learning process that is the responsibility of the lecturer. The main objective of the training program is to address the gap between an employee's and the organizations expected capabilities with respect to the duties that the employee is responsible for and the training can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the workforce in achieving predetermined job goals (Handoko 2001).

Lecturer's Performance

Performance of lecturers is the work achieved by lecturers based on their ability to perform tasks in the learning process which includes aspects of learning planning, implementation of learning process and assessment of learning outcomes. High lecturer performance must be a dream for lecturers. To know the performance success need to do performance appraisal. Performance appraisal with a task-centered approach is conducted by assessing employee behavior in accordance with its duties and responsibilities. When the training is done to the maximum in accordance with the needs and plans, it will affect the performance of a person. Preferably the training needs to be carried out intensively in accordance with the number and type of training that has been planned (Yani, 2012).

Research Methods

Characteristics of Respondents

Results of questionnaires processing based on higher education obtained sample data of the highest certification lecturer at State Polytechnic of Batam with the number of 27 people with percentage 36%. The sample of lecturers of certification based on the level of education is dominated by lecturers S2 graduates are 65 people with a percentage of 13%, while the remaining 13% is a graduate of S3.

The sample of lecturer certification based on the training that had been followed by five people who had never attended the training, attended one time training as many as 34 people, who attended twice as many as 16 people, attended three times as many as 13 people, and who participated in training more than three times as many as seven people.

Results and Discussion

Classic Assumption Test Results

Table 1

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Performance	.095	75	.093	.981	75	.320

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Source: Primary Data Processed Result, 2015

Based on Table 1, this normality test shows that the regression model with dependent lecturer performance already has normal distributed residual value. This is indicated by probability value Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is above 0.05.

Table 2
Multicollinearities Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Allowance	.954	1.048
Education	.598	1.673
Training	.602	1.661

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Primary Data Processed Result, 2015

From Table 2 it can be seen that all independent variables have a VIF value of less than 10. The result of the regression model test indicates the absence of multicollinearity symptoms in the regression model.

Table 3
Glejser Test

Model	Standardized	t	Sig.
(Constant)	Coefficients Beta		
1 Allowance	-.168	-1.426	.158
Education	-.174	-1.169	.246
Training	.035	.237	.814

a. Dependent Variable: ABRESID

Source: Primary Data Processed Result, 2015

From Table 3 it can be seen that all independent variables have a significance value above the value of α 0.05. The result of regression model test shows that all variables are free from heteroscedasticity.

Hypothesis Test

The first hypothesis proposed in this study states that there is a positive influence between the lecturer certification allowance on the performance of lecturers of several universities in Batam.

Table 4
Hypothesis Test Results 1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	t	Sig.
1	.293 ^a	.086	.073	2.617	.011

a. Predictors: (Constant), Allowance

b. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Primary Data Processed Result, 2015

Based on Table 4 above obtained the tribution of lecturer certification allowance amounted to 2.617 while t_{table} sought at $\alpha = 5\%$ with degrees of freedom (df) $n-k$ or $75-4 = 71$ is 1.6666 thus $t_{value} = 2,617 > t_{table} = 1.6666$ and a significance value of 0.011 (sig. > 0.05). Results also show Adjusted R Square of 0.073. This means that the performance of lecturers of several universities in Batam can be explained by 7.3% by the lecturer certification allowance variable, while the rest ($100\% - 7.3\% = 92.7\%$) is explained by other variables. The value of significance is less than 0.05 it can be concluded that hypothesis H1 can be supported.

The second hypothesis proposed in this study states that there is a positive influence between lecturers' education on the performance of lecturers of several universities in Batam.

Table 5
Hypothesis Test Results 2

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	t	Sig.
1	.695 ^a	.483	.476	8.266	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Education

b. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Primary Data Processed Result, 2015

Based on Table 5 above, it is obtained tcount of lecturers education variable equal to 8,266 whereas t_{table} is sought at $\alpha = 5\%$ with degrees of freedom (df) $n-k$ or $75-4 = 71$ is 1.6666 thus $t_{value} = 8,266 > t_{table} = 1.666$ and a significance value of 0.000 (sig. < 0.05). Results also show Adjusted R Square of 0.476. This means that the performance of lecturers of several universities in Batam can be explained by 47.6% by the lecturers education variables, while the rest ($100\% - 47.6\% = 52.4\%$) is explained by other variables. The value of significance is smaller than 0.05 it can be concluded that hypothesis H2 can be supported.

The third hypothesis proposed in this study states that there is a positive influence between lecturers training on the performance of lecturers of several universities in Batam.

Table 6
Hypothesis Test Results 3

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	t	Sig.
1	.591a	.349	.340	6.255	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Training

b. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source: Primary Data Processed Result, 2015

Based on Table 6, it is obtained t arithmetic lecturer training variable of 6.255 while t_{table} is sought at $\alpha = 5\%$ with degrees of freedom (df) $n-k$ or $75-4 = 71$ is 1.6666 thus $t_{value} = 6.255 > t_{table} = 1.666$ and a significance value of 0.000 (sig. < 0.05). The results also show Adjusted R Square of 0.340. This means that the performance of lecturers of several universities in Batam can be explained by 34% by lecturer training variables, while the rest (100% - 34% = 66%) is explained by other variables. The value of significance smaller than 0.05 then it can be concluded that hypothesis H3 can be supported.

Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis, hypothesis testing, and descriptive findings about lecturer certification allowance, lecturer education, and lecturer training, it can be concluded that the lecturer certification allowance, lecturer education, and lecturer training positively and significantly influence the performance of lecturers of several universities in Batam. This can be seen from the significance value of the variable allowance for lecturer certification, lecturer education, and lecturer training is smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that all hypotheses in this study are supported.

This study experiences the following limitations:

a. This study uses only three independent variables namely lecturer certification allowance, lecturer education, and lecturer training.

b. Performance appraisal used in the form of self-assessment (self-appraisal), so the data obtained about the performance has not described the actual performance of lecturers.

The implications of this research are:

a. The results of this study can be an input for the government in policy making and evaluation of government policies related to lecturer certification

allowance and the opportunity to continue education to a higher level for lecturers.

b. The results of this study can be one consideration for universities in policy-making related to the provision of training opportunities for lecturers to further improve the competence of lecturers.

The advice given are:

1. Further research may consider adding variables that may affect the performance of lecturers, including age, length of employment, job satisfaction, job skills, and leadership.

2. Further research for performance assessment should be done by looking at Employee Work Objectives for lecturers of Civil Servants and seeing the achievement of academic rank (the implementation of college tridharma) for private universities.

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